

The Influence of Service Quality and Customer Value on Customer Satisfaction at Seblak Gondez MSMEs Kepanjen, Malang Regency

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ABSTRACT: This study analyzes the influence of service quality and customer value on customer satisfaction at Seblak Gondez Kepanjen, a micro, small, and medium enterprise (MSME) in Malang Regency. A quantitative approach was used with data collected from 105 respondents through an offline questionnaire using purposive sampling. The data were analyzed using multiple linear regression and hypothesis testing. Descriptive results showed that respondents generally agreed or strongly agreed with the statements presented. The classical assumption test shows that the data meets the requirements of normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.688 indicates that 68.8% of the variation in customer satisfaction can be explained by the independent variables, while 3.12% is influenced by other factors. The t-test shows that service quality ($t = 5.042$, sig. 0.000) and customer value ($t = 4.450$, sig. 0.000) have a significant partial effect. The F-test shows a significant simultaneous effect ($F = 115.675$, sig. 0.000). This study concludes that there is an influence between service quality and customer value on customer satisfaction at the Seblak Gondez Kepanjen SME in Malang Regency.

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INTRODUCTION

Home-based industries or household industries are a growing business opportunity in this era as job opportunities become increasingly scarce. This type of industry can be managed anywhere, including at home, so it can be monitored daily. The food industry in Indonesia has experienced rapid growth, continuing to expand to over 10,000 units (cnbcindonesia.com (2024)). This business sector is dominated by restaurants or eateries that serve a variety of food and beverages. According to data from cnbcindonesia.com (2024), the food and beverage industry is the largest contributor to the non-oil and gas processing industry, which is the backbone of Indonesia's economy.

Seblak Gondez is a micro, small, and medium enterprise (MSME) that focuses on the growing trend of spicy food processing, making seblak a relevant choice in the culinary industry. With simple ingredients such as crackers, meatballs, sausages, noodles, and special seasonings, seblak is easy to prepare and can be varied according to consumer tastes.

According to Kotler and Keller (2018), customer satisfaction is the feeling of pleasure or disappointment that a person experiences as a result of comparing performance (results) with consumer expectations. Customer satisfaction needs to be taken into account because a company's consumers are crucial to its survival.

In order to achieve customer satisfaction during the purchasing process, businesses must maintain the quality of their services to ensure they remain excellent and outperform their competitors. Satisfactory service quality is one of the factors that determine the success and quality of a business. This service quality must be given special attention, as it is one of the factors influencing customer satisfaction. The higher the quality of service provided, the better the customer satisfaction achieved.

According to Kotler and Armstrong in Indrasari, (2019:61) "service quality is the totality of the features and characteristics of a product or service that support its ability to satisfy needs directly or indirectly." In their research, Wawi et al. (2022) stated that

service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction, while Haris (2023) stated that service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction.

In addition to service quality, customer value is also a factor that shapes customer satisfaction. Customer value is the perception or view of a product/company. Customer value can be described as an overall assessment of the benefits received by consumers compared to the costs incurred and the sacrifices made to obtain those benefits. According to Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller, customer value is defined as the difference between the benefits obtained by customers and the costs incurred (Riadi, 2020). In their research, Nurhalimah et al (2022) stated that customer value affects customer satisfaction. Furthermore, Usvela and Gunawan (2019) stated that customer value has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction.

Referring to the background described above, this study aims to analyze the influence of service quality and customer value on customer satisfaction at the Gondez seblak MSME in Kepanjen, Malang Regency. This study aims to provide an understanding of how to design marketing strategies that are more efficient and responsive to customer needs, especially amid increasingly fierce competition in the MSME sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing

Kotler and Armstrong (2016: 27) “marketing is meeting needs profitability” means that marketing is an activity carried out by an organization or institution to meet consumer needs in a way that benefits all parties involved. Another opinion is also expressed by Indrasari (2019: 2), namely marketing is a comprehensive, integrated, and planned activity, carried out by an organization in doing business in order to be able to accommodate market demand by creating products of selling value, determining prices, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offers of value to users, clients, partners, and the general public.

Marketing Management

Kotler & Keller (2016: 27), marketing management is the art and science of selecting target markets and reaching, retaining, and growing customers by creating, delivering, and communicating superior customer value. Meanwhile, according to Indrasari (2019: 8) marketing management is a series of processes for analyzing, planning, implementing, and monitoring and controlling a marketing activity where the aim is to achieve company targets effectively and efficiently.

Quality of Service

Service quality is one of the important indicators for companies to survive amid fierce competition in the industry. Service quality is defined as the totality of the characteristics of a product that support its ability to satisfy specified or defined needs. According to Tjiptono (2019:306), "Service quality is the level of excellence expected and control over that excellence to meet customer desires. According to Tjiptono (2019:306), there are several indicators that identify service quality variables, which can be seen from five indicators, namely:Tangibles(bukti fisik)

1. Reliability(keandalan)
2. Responsiveness (daya tanggap)
3. Assurance(Jaminan)
4. Empathy(Empati)

Customer Value

Simply put, customer value refers to the difference between the benefits consumers obtain through access to or ownership and use of a product or service, and the costs incurred to obtain those benefits. Tjiptono (2015) argues that there are several measures or indicators of customer value, consisting of:

1. Emotional Value
2. Social Value
3. Quality Value
4. Price Value

Customer Satisfaction

According to Kotler and Keller (2016:6), “Satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment that a person experiences when comparing the perceived performance or results of a product or service with their expectations.” If the performance or experience does not meet expectations, then customers will feel dissatisfied. If reality matches expectations, then customers will feel satisfied. And if reality exceeds expectations, then customers will feel very satisfied or happy. There are several indicators according to Kotler & Keller (2016:6), namely:

1. Satisfied with service
2. Satisfied with product
3. Satisfied with company
4. Satisfied overall

RESEARCH METHODS

This study aims to determine the effect of service quality and customer value on customer satisfaction at Seblak Gondez Kepanjen, a micro, small, and medium enterprise (MSME) in Malang Regency. This study was conducted to determine how service quality and customer value affect customer satisfaction. The scope of this study uses independent variables, namely Service Quality (X1) and Customer Value (X2), while the dependent variable in this study is Customer Satisfaction (Y) at the Seblak Gondez Kepanjen MSME in Malang Regency.

This study uses a quantitative research design. Primary data was collected through questionnaires distributed directly to respondents. The measurement tools were based on indicators taken from relevant theories, including Tjiptono's theory on service quality and customer value, as well as Kotler and Keller's theory on customer satisfaction. To ensure the validity and reliability of the data, this study includes validity and reliability tests of the research measurement tools. Data analysis consists of several stages: descriptive statistical analysis, classical assumption tests (normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity), multiple linear regression analysis, and hypothesis testing using t-tests (partial) and F-tests (simultaneous). The coefficient of determination (R^2) was also calculated to determine the proportion of variance in customer satisfaction explained by the independent variables.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 Quality of Service Validity Test Result

Variable	Item	r count	r table	Sig.	α	Information
Quality of Service (X1)	X1.1.1	0,525	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.1.2	0,551	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.1.3	0,546	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.2.1	0,581	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.2.2	0,453	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.3.1	0,473	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.3.2	0,507	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.4.1	0,443	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.4.2	0,514	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.4.3	0,529	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.4.4	0,408	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.5.1	0,505	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.5.2	0,480	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.5.3	0,505	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid

Table 2 Customer Value Validity Test Result

Customer Value (X2)	X2.1.1	0,551	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.1.2	0,554	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.2.1	0,596	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.2.2	0, 612	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.3.1	0,535	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.3.2	0,592	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.3.3	0,530	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.4.1	0, 560	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.4.2	0, 600	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid

Table 3 Customer Satisfaction Validity Test Result

Customer Satisfaction (Y)	Y1.1.1	0,524	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.1.2	0,557	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.1.3	0,581	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.2.1	0,51	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.2.2	0,530	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.3.1	0,582	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.3.2	0,582	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.4.1	0,581	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.4.2	0,541	0.1614	0,000	0,05	Valid

Source : Processed data (2025)

Based on field observations of 105 respondents who assessed service quality and customer value in relation to customer satisfaction at the Seblak Gondez Kepanjen MSME in Malang Regency. Before analyzing the data, the instruments used were first tested using the SPSS Statistics 26 calculation application as follows. The results of the validity test above indicate that all statement items used as measurement tools for the variables of service quality (X1), customer value (X2), and customer satisfaction (Y) are valid. This is evidenced by the fact that all statement items in each variable have a calculated r value greater than the table r value (0.1614) at a significance level of <math><0.05</math>. Therefore, the items of the service quality (X1), customer value (X2), and customer satisfaction (Y) variables can measure the influence of service quality (X1), customer value (X2), and customer satisfaction (Y) on the Seblak Gondez Kepanjen SME in Malang Regency.

Table 4 Reliability Test Results

Reliability Test			
Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Standard	Information
Quality of Service (X1)	0,770	0,60	Reliebel
Customer Value (X2)	0,738	0,60	Reliebel
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0,716	0,60	Reliebel

Source : Processed data (2025)

Based on Table 4, the reliability test results show that all variables have a Cronbach alpha value of more than 0.60. This indicates that the items of service quality (X1), customer value (X2), and customer satisfaction (Y) variables are considered reliable as measurement tools for variables in the study.

Figure 1 Normality Test Results

Based on the results of normality testing using a normality probability diagram, the influence of service quality and customer value on customer satisfaction is in accordance with the basis for decision making in normality testing, namely if the data is scattered around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line or the histogram graph shows a normal distribution pattern, then the results of the normality test of this regression model meet the assumption of normality.

Table 5 Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Collinearity Statistics		Keterangan
	Tolerance	VIF	
Quality of Service (X1)	0,352	2,843	No Multicollinearity Occurs
Customer Value (X2)	0,352	2,843	No Multicollinearity Occurs

Source : Processed data (2025)

Based on Table 5 above, the multicollinearity test results show that the VIF values of the service quality and customer value variables have a tolerance > 0.10 and VIF < 10, so the independent variables can be said to have no multicollinearity.

Figure 1 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Based on Figure 2, the heteroscedasticity test results show that the points are scattered above and below the number 0 on the Y-axis. From this, it can be concluded that this regression model does not experience heteroscedasticity.

Table 1 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Coefficients ^a						Collinearity			
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF	
		B	Std. Error	Beta					
1	(Constant)	4.259	2.355		1.809	.073			
	Quality of Service	.334	.066	.466	5.042	.000	0.352	2.843	
	Customer Value	.378	.085	.411	4.450	.000	0.352	2.843	
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction									

Source: Processed data (2025)

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis test in the table above, a multiple linear regression model equation can be seen as follows:

$$Y = 4,259 + 0,334 X1 + 0,378 X2 + e$$

The multiple linear regression equation shows the direction of influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The explanation of the multiple linear regression equation is as follows :

1. Constant Value (a) = 4.259
A constant of 4.259 means that if all independent variables, namely service quality (X1) and customer value (X2), are ignored or assumed to be 0 (zero), then the customer satisfaction variable (Y) will be equal to the constant value of 4.259.
2. The regression coefficient value for the service quality variable (b1) = 0.334
The multiple regression coefficient value for service quality (X1) is 0.334, which is positive. This means that if there is an increase of 1 unit in the service quality variable and the customer value variable is assumed to be 0 (zero), then the customer satisfaction variable (Y) will increase by 0.334. Nilai koefisien regresi variabel nilai pelanggan (b2) = 0,378
3. The regression coefficient value of the customer value variable (b2) = 0.378
The multiple regression coefficient value for customer value (X2) is 0.378, which is positive. This means that if there is an increase of 1 unit in the customer value variable and the service quality variable is assumed to be 0 (zero), then the customer satisfaction variable (Y) will increase by 0.378.

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the variables of service quality (X1) and customer value (X2) that have the greatest contribution or influence on customer satisfaction (Y) are customer value (X2) with a coefficient of 0.378 compared to service quality (X1) with a coefficient of 0.334.

Table 7 Coefficient of Determination Analysis Results

Model	Adjusted (R ²)
1	0, 688

Source: Processed data (2025)

Based on Table 7, the results of the coefficient of determination (R^2) analysis show that the adjusted coefficient of determination R^2 obtained is 0.688, which means that the contribution of service quality and customer value to customer satisfaction at Seblak Gondez Kepanjen MSMEs in Malang Regency is 0.688 or 68.8%. The remaining 3.12% (100% - 68.8%) is influenced by variables outside the scope of this study.

Table 8 Partial Hypothesis Test Result

Variabel	thitung	ttabel	Sig.	Sig. Tabel	Keterangan
Quality of Service (X1)	5,042	1.659	0,000	0,05	Signifikan
Customer Value (X2)	4,450	1.659	0,000	0,05	Signifikan

Source : Processed data (2025)

1. H_a for Hypothesis 1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This is because the service quality variable has a t-value $>$ t-table, namely $5.042 > 1.659$, and is significant at $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on these criteria, it can be concluded that hypothesis (H_1), which states that service quality partially has a positive effect on customer satisfaction at the Seblak Gondez Kepanjen MSMEs in Malang Regency, is accepted.
2. H_a for Hypothesis 2 is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This is because the customer value variable has a t-value $>$ t-table, namely $4.450 > 1.659$, and is significant at $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on these criteria, it can be concluded that hypothesis (H_2), which states that customer value partially has a positive effect on customer satisfaction at the Seblak Gondez Kepanjen MSME in Malang Regency, is accepted.

Table 9 Simultaneous Hypothesis Test Result

Fhitung	Ftabel	Sig.	Sig. Tabel	Keterangan
115,675	2,69	0,000	0,05	Signifikan

Source : Processed data (2025)

Based on Table 9, the simultaneous hypothesis testing (F-test) above, it can be concluded that: H_a for hypothesis 3 is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This is because $F_{count} > F_{table}$, namely $115.675 > 2.69$ and significant $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on these criteria, it can be concluded that hypothesis (H_3), which states that service quality and customer value simultaneously have a positive effect on customer satisfaction at the Seblak Gondez Kepanjen MSMEs in Malang Regency, is accepted.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the research analysis conducted the following discussion can be made :

1. The Effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction

Based on the results of the analysis of service quality variables, the tangible indicator had the highest mean of 4.31. This means that respondents agreed with the tangible indicator, namely that Seblak Gondez Kepanjen MSMEs in Malang Regency provided appropriate tangible evidence, such as the completeness of seblak products, product arrangement, and an attractive location.

Based on the partial hypothesis testing that has been conducted, it can be concluded that the quality of service has a positive effect on customer satisfaction. This result is supported by the t-test results, where the calculated t-value (thitung) is greater than the critical t-value (ttabel), specifically $5.042 > 1.659$, and the p-value is significant at $0.000 < 0.05$. The findings of this study align with the hypothesis stating that service quality is expected to have a positive impact on customer satisfaction at the Seblak Gondez SME in Kepanjen, Malang Regency. This is because the service quality variable has the highest mean item, which is product arrangement. The product arrangement item has a mean of 4.37 and can be classified as a high mean. Seblak Gondez Kepanjen Malang Regency SMEs use service quality by providing good service to customers, empathy, and a positive attitude, such as being friendly, polite, and respectful to customers. The customer base is dominated by women aged 20-25 years old, with the characteristic occupation being students/college students. This is because individuals in their 20s generally have a busy and active lifestyle. Therefore, spicy food like Seblak Gondez is more suitable for their lifestyle, as they enjoy spicy food.

The results of this study support the findings of previous research conducted by Utu Purni Astuti and Andi Irfan, as well as Aminah (2023), who conducted a study titled "The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction at Warkop 51 Daya in Makassar City." The results of that study indicate that service quality has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction. Based on all the data obtained, it can be concluded that service quality has a positive impact on customer satisfaction at the Seblak Gondez Kepanjen UMKM in Malang Regency.

2. The Influence of Customer Value on Customer Satisfaction

Based on the results of the variable description analysis, customer value has an average of 4.24 and can be classified in the high mean category. The emotional value indicator is the indicator within the customer value variable with the highest mean, at 4.28. This means that, on average, respondents agree with the emotional value indicator, indicating that the UMKM Seblak Gondez Kepanjen can maintain its emotional value in terms of the positive feelings and benefits provided to customers, such as responding to comments appropriately and demonstrating empathy in communication, especially when handling customer complaints.

Based on the partial hypothesis testing that has been conducted, it can be concluded that customer value has a positive effect on customer satisfaction. This result is proven by the t-test results, where $t_{count} > t_{table}$, i.e., $4.450 > 1.659$, and is significant at $0.000 < 0.05$. The findings of this study align with the hypothesis stating that customer value is expected to have a positive impact on customer satisfaction at the Seblak Gondez Kepanjen SME in Malang Regency. This is because the customer value variable includes the item “emotional impression,” which has the highest mean of 4.41 and can be classified as a very high mean.

This study was dominated by women aged 20-25 years with job characteristics as customers/students. This is because people in their 20s generally have busy and active lifestyles. Therefore, spicy foods such as Seblak Gondez are more suited to their lifestyle, as they enjoy spicy foods. The results of this study support the findings of a previous study conducted by Husain et al. (2023) titled “The Influence of Customer Value on Customer Satisfaction at Az-Zahra Store in Gorontalo City.” The study concluded that customer value has a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction. Based on all the data obtained, it can be concluded that customer value has a positive effect on customer satisfaction at the Seblak Gondez SME in Kepanjen, Malang Regency.

3. The Influence of Service Quality and Customer Value on Customer Satisfaction

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination analysis, the Adjusted R Square was 0.688 or 68.8%, which means that the contribution of service quality and customer value to customer satisfaction at Seblak Gondez Kepanjen MSME in Malang Regency was 68.8%, while the remaining 3.12% was influenced by other variables not examined in this study. Based on the multiple linear regression analysis, it was found that the variable with the greatest contribution or influence on customer satisfaction is customer value, with a coefficient of 0.378 for customer value (X2), compared to service quality (X1) with a coefficient of 0.334. In this case, it can be said that the Seblak Gondez Kepanjen SME in Malang Regency has excellent customer value in terms of customer satisfaction. Based on the simultaneous hypothesis test conducted, it was found that the influence of service quality and customer value on customer satisfaction is positive. This result is proven by the F-test result, where $F_{calculated} > F_{table}$, i.e., $115.675 > 2.69$, and significant at $0.000 < 0.05$. The research results indicate that service quality and customer value simultaneously have a positive influence on customer satisfaction.

RESEARCH CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, the research results can be concluded as follows:

1. Service quality has a positive effect on customer satisfaction. This means that to improve customer satisfaction, good service quality is needed, including tangible evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.
2. Customer value partially has a positive effect on customer satisfaction. This means that to increase customer satisfaction, excellent customer value is required, including emotional value, social value, quality value, and price value.
3. Service quality and customer value simultaneously have a positive effect on customer satisfaction. This means that in order to increase customer satisfaction, it is necessary to have excellent service quality and customer value.

Suggestions

Based on the conclusions obtained, the suggestions that can be conveyed are :

1.) Suggestions for MSMEs Seblak Gondez Kepanjen Malang Regency

1. To improve customer satisfaction, excellent service quality is required. It is recommended that MSMEs Seblak Gondez Kepanjen should improve its responsiveness in terms of service speed, because the mean value for the responsiveness indicator is high, but the mean value for service speed is lower than that of other indicators.
2. To improve customer satisfaction, good customer value is required. It is recommended that MSMEs Seblak Gondez Kepanjen, Malang Regency, continue to optimize price value because the price value indicator shows the lowest mean value compared to other customer value indicators.

2.) Suggestions for Further Research

1. Future researchers are advised to add other indicators to make their research results more accurate and to expand the scope of their research area to generalize the research results.
2. It is recommended that future researchers add other variables.

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